

Deliverable 2.2

Workpackage WP2-T2

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D2.2 Sub-database for antimicrobial resistances (AMR db)

This deliverable consists of three Python scripts that connect the Biologics database (see D3.1.3) of the strains with the ResFinder database [EFSA 2021 \(2022-05-24\)](#) of the resistance genes. The first one (0) generates an Excel file, the second one (1) makes a graph about the number of genes detected for the different pathogens and the third one (2) makes a global graph comparing the coverage of the ResFinder database by CARE reference materials. The whole will permit to get the updates of the AMR database as long as the CARE collection will grow by successive strain deposits in the BRCs. The two graphs proposed permit a follow-up.

Excel spreadsheets are also possible outputs.

0_resfinder_data_vs_care_data.py

```
import urllib.request
import os
import pandas as pd
from os.path import isfile, join
from openpyxl.workbook.workbook import Workbook
from openpyxl.styles import Border, Side, Alignment, Font

### 0 - functions to style the Excel file
def redimension_cell_width(ws):
    dims = {}
    for row in ws.rows:
        for cell in row:
            if cell.value:
                line_max = len(str(cell.value))
                max_ = max((dims.get(cell.column_letter, 0), line_max))
                dims[cell.column_letter] = max_
    for col, value in dims.items():
        ws.column_dimensions[col].width = value+2

def borders_cells(sheet):
    thin = Side(border_style="thin", color="000000")

    for col in sheet.columns:
        for cell in col:
            if cell.value:
                cell.border = Border(top=thin, left=thin, right=thin, bottom=thin)
```



```
def style_sheet(sheet):
    header = list(sheet.rows)[0]
    for cell in header:
        cell.font = Font(bold=True)

    header2 = list(sheet.rows)[1]
    for cell in header2:
        cell.font = Font(bold=True)

    for col in sheet.rows:
        cell = col[0]
        cell.font = Font(bold=True)

def style_sheet2(sheet):
    header = list(sheet.rows)[0]
    for cell in header:
        cell.font = Font(bold=True)

    for col in sheet.rows:
        cell = col[0]
        cell.font = Font(bold=True)

def merge_headers(sheet, header):
    value = header[1]
    count = 0
    for i in range(1, len(header)):
        if header[i] != value:
            sheet.merge_cells(start_row=1, start_column=i-count+1, end_row=1,
end_column=i)
            value = header[i]
            count = 1
        else:
            count += 1

### I - we read the phenotypes.txt file of the resfinder database from the internet
lines = []
link = "https://bitbucket.org/genomicepidemiology/resfinder_db/raw/fa32d9a3cf0c12ec70ca4e90c45c0d590ee810bd/phenotypes.txt"
with urllib.request.urlopen(link) as url:
    s = str(url.read())
```



```
# then we analyse it to get the genes and the classes associated to each gene
genes_rb = []
classes_rb = []
for elmt in s.split('\n'):
    if '\t' in elmt:
        genes_rb.append(elmt.split('\t')[0].split('_')[0])
        classes_rb.append(elmt.split('\t')[1])
    else:
        print(elmt)

genes_rb.append('mcr-1')
classes_rb.append('Polymyxin')

# background check: we must have as many genes as groups of classes
if len(genes_rb) != len(classes_rb):
    print("trouble!")

### II - then we open the CARE files with the results of the genotypes obtained in
resfinder
local_path = 'C:/Users/mboutrou/Documents/'
#local_path = '/mnt/gaia/my_home/'
path = local_path+'TR_AMR_database_pour_CARE'
dir_list = os.listdir(path)

genus_par_classe = {}
names_classes = {}
genes_par_classes_par_genus = {}
genes_par_classes = {}
# there is one file for each genus
for f in dir_list:
    genus = f.split('.')[0]
    print(genus)

    genes_genus = {}
    genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus] = {}

xlsx = pd.ExcelFile(path+'/' +f)
sheet_names = xlsx.sheet_names # see all sheet names

# I try to locate the genotype column located in one of the sheets
for sheet_name in sheet_names:
    sheet = pd.read_excel(xlsx, sheet_name)
```



```
col_care = -1
for col in range(len(sheet.columns)):
    if sheet.columns[col] == 'Genotype':
        col_care = col

if col_care != -1:
    for i in range(1, len(sheet)):
        # then for each line I explode the genotypes cell to get the different genes
listed
        care_id = sheet.iloc[i, col_care]
        genes = care_id.split(' ')

        # and I add one occurrence of this gene on the list of genes for this genus
(genes_genus)
        # and also one occurrence for the corresponding class of genes on the list of
classes for this genus
        for gene in genes:
            gene = gene.replace('oqx', 'Oqx')
            gene = gene.replace('strA', 'aph(3\\)-Ib')

            if gene in genes_rb:
                idx = genes_rb.index(gene)
                classe = classes_rb[idx]
                if classe not in genes_genus:
                    genes_genus[classe] = {}

            if gene not in genes_genus[classe]:
                genes_genus[classe][gene] = 0
                genes_genus[classe][gene] += 1

            if classe not in names_classes:
                names_classes[classe] = []
            if gene not in names_classes[classe]:
                names_classes[classe].append(gene)

            if classe not in genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus]:
                genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus][classe] = []
            if gene not in genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus][classe]:
                genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus][classe].append(gene)
            if classe not in genes_par_classes:
                genes_par_classes[classe] = []
            if gene not in genes_par_classes[classe]:
                genes_par_classes[classe].append(gene)
```



```
genus_par_classe[genus] = genes_genus
```

```
### III - then I can start creating the final Excel
```

```
wb = Workbook()
```

```
# we create the first sheet
```

```
# the different genes are the headline and the different genus are the headrow
```

```
# each cell contain the number of occurrence for the genus at the beginning of the row  
and the gene at the top of the column
```

```
header = [""]
```

```
header2 = [""]
```

```
for n_c in names_classes:
```

```
    for g_c in names_classes[n_c]:
```

```
        header.append(n_c)
```

```
        header2.append(g_c)
```

```
rows = []
```

```
for genus in genus_par_classe:
```

```
    row = [genus]
```

```
    for i in range(1, len(header)):
```

```
        c_i = header[i]
```

```
        g_i = header2[i]
```

```
        if c_i in genus_par_classe[genus] and g_i in genus_par_classe[genus][c_i]:
```

```
            row.append(genus_par_classe[genus][c_i][g_i])
```

```
        else:
```

```
            row.append(0)
```

```
    rows.append(row)
```

```
sheet = wb.create_sheet("Resistance_genes_used")
```

```
sheet.append(header)
```

```
sheet.append(header2)
```

```
for row in rows:
```

```
    sheet.append(row)
```

```
# and then we style the sheet
```

```
redimension_cell_width(sheet)
```

```
borders_cells(sheet)
```

```
style_sheet(sheet)
```

```
merge_headers(sheet, header)
```



```
# we create the second sheet
# it's the same thing than the first sheet but with the classes instead of the genes as
the headline
header3 = list(set(header))
header3.sort()

rows = []
for genus in genes_par_classes_par_genus:
    row = [genus]
    sum = 0

    for i in range(1, len(header3)):
        c_i = header3[i]

        if c_i in genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus]:
            row.append(len(genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus][c_i]))
            sum += len(genes_par_classes_par_genus[genus][c_i])
        else:
            row.append(0)

    row.append(sum)
    rows.append(row)

row_final = ["All genera combined"]
sum_final = 0
for i in range(1, len(header3)):
    c_i = header3[i]

    if c_i in genes_par_classes:
        row_final.append(len(genes_par_classes[c_i]))
        sum_final += len(genes_par_classes[c_i])
    else:
        row_final.append(0)

row_final.append(sum_final)
rows.append(row_final)

sheet = wb.create_sheet("Statistics")
header3.append("All classes combined")
sheet.append(header3)
for row in rows:
    sheet.append(row)

total_resfinder = ["Total ResFinder"]
```



```
sum_res = 0
for i in range(1, len(header3)-1):
    c_f = header3[i]
    total_resfinder.append(classes_rb.count(c_f))
    sum_res += classes_rb.count(c_f)
total_resfinder.append(sum_res)
sheet.append(total_resfinder)
```

```
# we style the sheet
redimension_cell_width(sheet)
borders_cells(sheet)
style_sheet2(sheet)
```

```
# then finally we save the Excel
del wb["Sheet"]
path_excel = local_path+'bilan_genes.xlsx'
wb.save(str(path_excel))
```

1_plot_genus_results.py

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import matplotlib
import seaborn as sns
from matplotlib.ticker import FormatStrFormatter
import textwrap
```

```
# function to write properly the ylabels
def wrap_labels(ax, width, break_long_words=False):
    labels = []
    for label in ax.get_yticklabels():
        text = label.get_text()
        labels.append(textwrap.fill(text, width=width,
                                   break_long_words=break_long_words))
    ax.set_yticklabels(labels, rotation=0)
```

```
# we open the statistics sheet we created before
xls_resfinder = pd.ExcelFile('C:/Users/mboutrou/Documents/bilan_genes.xlsx')
df = pd.read_excel(xls_resfinder, 'Statistics', index_col=0)
```

```
# we keep the rows concerning the genes and we transpose them
for name in df.columns:
    if name == 'All classes combined':
```



```
df = df.drop(name, 1)
df = df.T
for name in df.columns:
    if name == 'All genera combined' or name == 'Total ResFinder':
        df = df.drop(name, 1)
print(df)

# we organize the plot with a linear scale
plt.rcParams["figure.figsize"] = (20,8)
ax = df.plot(kind="barh", width = 0.8)
wrap_labels(ax, 30)
plt.title("Number of resistance genes per genus per antimicrobial class")
plt.xlabel("Number of resistance genes")
plt.ylabel("Antimicrobial classes")
plt.yticks(fontsize=8)
plt.gcf().subplots_adjust(left=0.2)
plt.xscale("linear")
plt.ylim(-0.5, len(plt.gca().get_yticklabels())-0.5)
for i in range(len(plt.gca().get_yticklabels())):
    plt.gca().axhline(i+0.5, color = 'gray', linestyle = '-', linewidth = 0.7)
plt.savefig('C:/Users/mboutrou/Documents/genes_results.png')
```

2_plot_global_results.py

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import matplotlib
import seaborn as sns
from matplotlib.ticker import FormatStrFormatter
import textwrap

# function to write properly the ylabels
def wrap_labels(ax, width, break_long_words=False):
    labels = []
    for label in ax.get_yticklabels():
        text = label.get_text()
        labels.append(textwrap.fill(text, width=width,
                                   break_long_words=break_long_words))
    ax.set_yticklabels(labels, rotation=0)

# we open the statistics sheet we created before
xls_resfinder = pd.ExcelFile('C:/Users/mboutrou/Documents/bilan_genes.xlsx')
df = pd.read_excel(xls_resfinder, 'Statistics', index_col=0)
```



```
# we keep the global rows (the one about CARE and the one about ResFinder) and we transpose them
```

```
df = df.T
```

```
for name in df.columns:
```

```
    if name != 'All genera combined' and name != 'Total ResFinder':
```

```
        df = df.drop(name, 1)
```

```
print(df)
```

```
# we organize the plot with a log scale
```

```
plt.rcParams["figure.figsize"] = (20,8)
```

```
ax = df.plot(kind="barh", width = 0.8)
```

```
wrap_labels(ax, 30)
```

```
plt.title("Number of resistance genes per antimicrobial class in CARE vs in ResFinder")
```

```
plt.xlabel("Number of resistance genes")
```

```
plt.ylabel("Antimicrobial classes")
```

```
plt.yticks(fontsize=8)
```

```
plt.gcf().subplots_adjust(left=0.2)
```

```
plt.xscale("log")
```

```
plt.gca().get_xaxis().set_major_formatter(matplotlib.ticker.ScalarFormatter())
```

```
plt.ylim(-0.5, len(plt.gca().get_yticklabels())-0.5)
```

```
for i in range(len(plt.gca().get_yticklabels())):
```

```
    plt.gca().axhline(i+0.5, color = 'gray', linestyle = '-', linewidth = 0.7)
```

```
plt.savefig('C:/Users/mboutrou/Documents/global_results.png')
```

Graph 1 :

Graph 2 :

Excel table :

	Aminoglycoside	Amphenicol	Amphenicol, Quinolone, Quaternary Ammonium Compounds, Folate pathway antagonist	Beta-lactam	Folate pathway antagonist	Fosfomycin	Lincosamide	Lincosamide, Streptogramin A, Pleuromutilin	Macrolide	Macrolide, Lincosamide, Streptogramin B	Peroxide	Polymyxin	Quaternary Ammonium Compound	Quinolone	Streptogramin A	Tetracycline	Total per pathogen
Salmonella	14	3	2	8	7	1	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	3	44
Staphylococcus	4	1	0	3	1	0	1	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	18
Escherichia	11	3	0	4	8	0	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	0	0	4	36
Yersinia	11	3	0	4	4	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	4	31
Campylobacter	4	0	0	9	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	16
Total per class	30	6	2	26	11	2	4	2	3	3	1	4	1	1	10	107	
Total ResFinder	261	41	2	2013	163	41	12	13	39	79	1	57	9	126	14	148	3019